

Data Availability

References	Link
[1] 8 Essential foods to eat before a run(stock up your kitchen). (2024, February 23). <i>fitness first</i> . https://www.fitnessfirst.co.uk/blog/8-essential-foods-to-eat-before-a-run-stock-up-your-kitchen#:~:text=3)%20PORRIDGE,something%20small%20to%20sustain%20them.%E2%80%9D	https://www.fitnessfirst.co.uk/blog/8-essential-foods-to-eat-before-a-run-stock-up-your-kitchen#:~:text=3)%20PORRIDGE,something%20small%20to%20sustain%20them.%E2%80%9D
[2] Antara. (2025, April 13). ChatGPT Lampau Instagram dan TikTok sebagai Aplikasi Paling Banyak Diunduh Maret 2025. <i>ChatGPT Lampau Instagram Dan TikTok Sebagai Aplikasi Paling Banyak Diunduh Maret 2025 - TIMES Indonesia</i> . https://timesindonesia.co.id/tekno/534840/chatgpt-lampau-instagram-dan-tiktok-sebagai-aplikasi-paling-banyak-diunduh-maret-2025	https://timesindonesia.co.id/tekno/534840/chatgpt-lampau-instagram-dan-tiktok-sebagai-aplikasi-paling-banyak-diunduh-maret-2025
[3] Barzam. (2018, January 20). <i>8 Strategi Komunikasi dalam Pembentukan Opini Publik - PakarKomunikasi.com</i> . https://pakarkomunikasi.com/strategi-komunikasi-dalam-pembentukan-opini-publik	https://pakarkomunikasi.com/strategi-komunikasi-dalam-pembentukan-opini-publik
[4] Choi, J., Lee, S., Choi, H., Lee, J., Lee, N., Oh, H., Kwon, H., & Kwon, J. (2023). Fermented gold kiwi prevents and attenuates chronic Alcohol-Induced liver injury in mice via suppression of inflammatory responses. <i>Applied Sciences</i> , 13(3), 1877. https://doi.org/10.3390/app13031877	https://doi.org/10.3390/app13031877
[5] <i>Complete guide to Instagram content types Learn at Microsoft Create</i> . (n.d.). https://create.microsoft.com/en-us/learn/articles/complete-guide-instagram-content-types	https://create.microsoft.com/en-us/learn/articles/complete-guide-instagram-content-types
[6] Effendy, J. A., & Keitaro, K. (2022). THE EFFECT OF INSTAGRAM CONTENT TOWARDS INTENTION TO VISIT UC_IBMRC WITH ONLINE ENGAGEMENT AS MEDIATING VARIABLE. <i>International Journal of Economics Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)</i> , 5(3). https://doi.org/10.29040/ijebar.v5i3.3021	https://doi.org/10.29040/ijebar.v5i3.3021
[7] Jansen, D. (2025a, March 23). <i>What (Exactly) is discourse analysis?</i> Grad Coach. https://gradcoach.com/discourse-analysis-101/	https://gradcoach.com/discourse-analysis-101/
[8] Kemp, S. (2025, March 23). <i>Digital 2025: top social platforms in 2025 — DataReportal – Global Digital Insights</i> . DataReportal – Global Digital Insights. https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2025-sub-section-top-social-platforms	https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2025-sub-section-top-social-platforms
[9] Kosmos, P. (2023, November 23). <i>Cara Memilihan Teknik Analisis Data yang Tepat Dan Benar</i> . https://dac.telkomuniversity.ac.id/cara-memilihan-teknik-analisis-data-yang-tepat-dan-benar/#:~:text=Teknik%20analisis%20data%20kualitatif,-Teknik%20ini%20dig	https://dac.telkomuniversity.ac.id/cara-memilihan-teknik-analisis-data-yang-tepat-dan-benar/#:~:text=Teknik%20analisis%20data%20kualitatif,-Teknik%20ini%20dig

<p>https://dac.telkomuniversity.ac.id/cara-memilihan-teknik-analisis-data-yang-tepat-dan-benar/#:~:text=Teknik%20analisis%20data%20kualitatif,-Teknik%20ini%20digunakan&text=Data%20kualitatif%20dapat%20berupa%20teks,menginterpretasikan%20makna%20dari%20data%20tersebut</p>	<p>unakan&text=Data%20kualitatif%20dapat%20berupa%20teks,menginterpretasikan%20makna%20dari%20data%20tersebut</p>
<p>[10] Nanda, S., & Nanda, S. (2025, March 12). Metode penelitian kualitatif: pengertian, jenis, & contoh. <i>Portal Belajar & Latihan Soal Terlengkap Blog Brain Academy</i>. https://www.brainacademy.id/blog/metode-penelitian-kualitatif</p>	<p>https://www.brainacademy.id/blog/metode-penelitian-kualitatif</p>
<p>[11] Salma, N. (2024, August 29). Instagram VS TikTok, Dua Media Sosial Populer di Indonesia 2024 - Sukabumi update. <i>Sukabumi Update</i>. https://www.sukabumiupdate.com/gadget/146331/instagram-vs-tiktok-dua-media-sosial-populer-di-indonesia-2024</p>	<p>https://www.sukabumiupdate.com/gadget/146331/instagram-vs-tiktok-dua-media-sosial-populer-di-indonesia-2024</p>
<p>[12] Srivastava, T. (2024, March 21). <i>72-Hour fruit diet expert shares pros cons and potential risks</i>. Onlymyhealth. https://www.onlymyhealth.com/pros-cons-and-potential-risks-of-seventy-two-hour-fruit-diet-1710875660</p>	<p>https://www.onlymyhealth.com/pros-cons-and-potential-risks-of-seventy-two-hour-fruit-diet-1710875660</p>
<p>[13] Statista. (2025, March 26). <i>Most used social networks 2025, by number of users</i>. https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/</p>	<p>https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/</p>
<p>[14] <i>The Correspondence Theory of Truth (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy)</i>. (2015, May 28). https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/truth-correspondence/</p>	<p>https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/truth-correspondence/</p>
<p>[15] Zhou, M., Zhang, N., Zhang, M., & Ma, G. (2020). Culture, eating behavior, and infectious disease control and prevention. <i>Journal of Ethnic Foods</i>, 7(1). https://doi.org/10.1186/s42779-020-00076-y</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1186/s42779-020-00076-y</p>
<p>[16] Nasery, M., Turel, O., Yuan, Y. Combating Fake News on Social Media: A Framework, Review, and Future Opportunities (2023) <i>Communications of the Association for Information Systems</i>, 53, pp. 833-876. https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85169086183&doi=10.17705%2f1CAIS.05335&partnerID=40&md5=a3ca76b6c2d5b4c5fa3914e88259090a</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85169086183&doi=10.17705%2f1CAIS.05335&partnerID=40&md5=a3ca76b6c2d5b4c5fa3914e88259090a</p>
<p>[17] Diekman, C., Ryan, C.D., Oliver, T.L. Misinformation and Disinformation in Food Science and Nutrition: Impact on Practice (2023) <i>Journal of Nutrition</i>, 153 (1), pp. 3-9. https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85150149752&doi=10.1016%2fj.tjn.2022.10.001&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85150149752&doi=10.1016%2fj.tjn.2022.10.001&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>

<p>0-85150149752&doi=10.1016%2fj.tjnut.2022.10.001&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>	
<p>[18] Shu, K. Combating disinformation on social media: A computational perspective (2022) BenchCouncil Transactions on Benchmarks, Standards and Evaluations, 2 (1), art. no. 100035, https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85144850116&doi=10.1016%2fj.tbench.2022.100035&partnerID=40&md5=345602d1fd4e28199ece50218253cd</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85144850116&doi=10.1016%2fj.tbench.2022.100035&partnerID=40&md5=345602d1fd4e28199ece50218253cd</p>
<p>[19] Ferreira, R.R. Liquid Disinformation Tactics: Overcoming Social Media Countermeasures through Misleading Content (2022) Journalism Practice, 16 (8), pp. 1537-1558. https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104511827&doi=10.1080%2f17512786.2021.1914707&partnerID=40&md5=aa2293f9e8310d0a0d2d500beaf1c02c</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85104511827&doi=10.1080%2f17512786.2021.1914707&partnerID=40&md5=aa2293f9e8310d0a0d2d500beaf1c02c</p>
<p>[20] Baker, S.A., Wade, M., Walsh, M.J. The challenges of responding to misinformation during a pandemic: content moderation and the limitations of the concept of harm (2020) Media International Australia, 177 (1), pp. 103-107. https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85089687957&doi=10.1177%2f1329878X20951301&partnerID=40&md5=c8dc3ab3e113d809a542cf8cf5f47a09</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85089687957&doi=10.1177%2f1329878X20951301&partnerID=40&md5=c8dc3ab3e113d809a542cf8cf5f47a09</p>
<p>[21] Talwar, S., Dhir, A., Singh, D., Virk, G.S., Salo, J. Sharing of fake news on social media: Application of the honeycomb framework and the third-person effect hypothesis (2020) Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services, 57, art. no. 102197, https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85087395502&doi=10.1016%2fj.jretconser.2020.102197&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85087395502&doi=10.1016%2fj.jretconser.2020.102197&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>
<p>[22] Bhanbhro, S., Kamal, T., Diyo, R.W., Lipoeto, N.I., Soltani, H. Factors affecting maternal nutrition and health: A qualitative study in a matrilineal community in Indonesia (2020) PLoS ONE, 15 (6 June), art. no. e0234545, https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086625290&doi=10.1371%2fjournal.pone.0234545&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85086625290&doi=10.1371%2fjournal.pone.0234545&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>
<p>[23] Alharthi, R., Alhothali, A., Moria, K. Detecting and Characterizing Arab Spammers Campaigns in Twitter (2019) Procedia Computer Science, 163, pp. 248-256. https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85081156829&doi=10.1016%2fj.procs.2019.12.106&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85081156829&doi=10.1016%2fj.procs.2019.12.106&partnerID=40&md5=2f459b412505e3399c4bf7236715f4fe</p>

<p>0-85081156829&doi=10.1016%2fj.procs.2019.12.106 &partnerID=40&md5=</p>	
<p>[24] Shao, C., Ciampaglia, G.L., Varol, O., Yang, K.-C., Flammini, A., Menczer, F. The spread of low-credibility content by social bots (2018) <i>Nature Communications</i>, 9 (1), art. no. 4787, https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85056802427&doi=10.1038%2fs41467-018-06930-7&partnerID=40&md5</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85056802427&doi=10.1038%2fs41467-018-06930-7&partnerID=40&md5</p>
<p>[25] LaDonna, K.A., Ghavanini, A.A., Venance, S.L. Truths and misinformation: a qualitative exploration of myotonic dystrophy (2015) <i>The Canadian journal of neurological sciences. Le journal canadien des sciences neurologiques</i>, 42 (3), pp. 187-194. https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85018214553&doi=10.1017%2fcjn.2015.26&partnerID=40&md5=807758</p>	<p>https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85018214553&doi=10.1017%2fcjn.2015.26&partnerID=40&md5=807758</p>
<p>[26] Nugroho, M. R. P., Haerunisa, H., Izati, M. P., Ramadhanty, S., & Firmansyah, B. (2024). Analisis Pembelajaran Literasi Keuangan Melalui Konten Video: Tinjauan pada Short Video TikTok. <i>Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Pendidikan</i>, 21(1), 14–19. https://doi.org/10.21831/jep.v21i1.72851</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.21831/jep.v21i1.72851</p>
<p>[27] Postelnicu, & Monica. (2014, March 15). <i>Two-step flow model of communication Mass Media, Opinion Leaders & Audience Impact</i>. Encyclopedia Britannica. https://www.britannica.com/topic/two-step-flow-model-of-communication</p>	<p>https://www.britannica.com/topic/two-step-flow-model-of-communication</p>
<p>[28]https://www.facebook.com/CNNIndonesia. (2019b, November 12). 5 Fakta tentang Nasi Putih. <i>Gaya Hidup</i>. https://www.cnnindonesia.com/gaya-hidup/20191112135900-255-447640/5-fakta-tentang-nasi-putih#:~:text=Memicu%20alergi,dengan%20gejala%20muntah%20dan%20diare.</p>	<p>https://www.cnnindonesia.com/gaya-hidup/20191112135900-255-447640/5-fakta-tentang-nasi-putih#:~:text=Memicu%20alergi,dengan%20gejala%20muntah%20dan%20diare.</p>